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Environmental policy is a set of policies aimed at protecting and improving the natural environment around us, effective use of natural resources and their enrichment, taking into account the requirements and recommendations of environmental science. As a rule, such a policy can be carried out in a state, regional and global framework and provide for the creation and compliance with legal frameworks (laws) nature conservation.

In recent years, the USA, Japan, many countries of Western Europe and the CIS (especially Uzbekistan) have developed the necessary regulatory legal acts, adopted laws aimed at improving the difficult environmental situation, and began to apply them in practice. Popular movements and parties aimed at improving the environment have become active in them (for example, the Greens, Greenpeace, Ecosan, the environmental movement, etc.).

THE IMPACT OF THE CHEMICAL INDUSTRY ON THE ENVIRONMENT

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ABSTRACT

The current dynamic age is impossible without the chemical industry. The chemical industry is used in all areas. At the same time, a lot of harmful substances and gases are released with the produced. This leads to environmental pollution, harmful gases in nature, pollution of reservoirs. Pollution of nature causes the growth of diseases. To avoid this, it is necessary to use waste-free technologies

Environmental pollution is understood as an excess of substances or toxic substances that do not have a natural character, the structure and composition of which are unknown.

The following types of environmental pollution can be distinguished: physical (noise, electromagnetic, radiomagnetic, radiation), chemical (heavy metals, peptides, plastics), biological (biogenic, microbiological, genetic), informational (false messages, risk factors).

Environmental pollution is caused by natural and anthropogenic factors.

Natural factors are understood as environmental pollution, primarily by natural means - lightning emissions, burning of grasses and forests, volcanic eruptions, wind movement, rotting (plant and animal residues) and other processes

occurring continuously in the biosphere. These natural factors emit millions of tons of dust and dust into the air per year.

But at present, the participation of artificial factors (anthropogenic process) in the pollution of nature is also largely observed. It accounts for 2/3 of emissions into the atmosphere.

As a result of environmental pollution, the flora and fauna of the earth's surface, centuries-old historical monuments and structures suffer equally. There is an opinion among our people that "the water becomes clear when the seven is spinning." Indeed, if nature is in moderation, it will have such a unique property as disinfection, purification of various wastewater, waste. We know that the gas (CO₂) emitted into the atmosphere is continuously processed by plants through the process of photosynthesis, converted into oxygen and returned back to nature. However, emissions into nature in recent periods exceed the norm at such a level that, as a result, nature increasingly loses its ability to self-repair, purification.

Any chemical contamination is the ingress of a chemical substance into an environment unusual for it. Harmful emissions resulting from human activity are

characterized by catastrophic consequences for the environment.

Waste can lead to serious damage, chronic diseases and even mutations. For example, heavy metals accumulate in plants and living organisms and have a toxic effect on them. Chlorine dioxin, which, in addition to heavy metals, is considered particularly harmful, is released as a residual substance when obtaining a herbicide from chlorine-containing derivatives of aromatic hydrocarbons. Again, this substance is separated from cellulose as a residue in paper production, as well as in the metallurgical industry. This substance is very harmful to humans and animals, even in small amounts it damages major organs such as the liver, kidneys and immune system.

At the same time, emissions into the environment lead to the fact that the circulation of substances in nature is also disrupted.

Pollution on earth is divided into pollution in the layers of the atmosphere, lithosphere and hydrosphere.

Layers of the earth	Source of pollution	Harmful substances
Atmosphere	Manufacturing industry Transport Thermal stations	Carbon, nitrogen, sulfur oxides, organic compounds, industrial dust
Hydrosphere	Waste water Oil leaks Motor transport	Heavy metals, oil, petroleum products
Lithosphere	Sonatas and agricultural waste, Multiple use of minerals	Plastics, rubber, heavy metals

Along with the circulation of substances in nature, harmful components are divided into species that spread over the entire surface of the earth, into separate areas or local territories. For this reason, environmental crises are divided into 3 types: global, regional and local.

An increase in the CO₂ content in the atmosphere can be cited as one of the global problems. As a sad consequence of this, the increase in temperature led to the emergence of the so-called "greenhouse effect". The disruption of carbon circulation in nature turns from an environmental problem into an economic, sociological and ultimately political problem. Indeed, the heating regime of the sun began to be disrupted as a result of the fact that the atmosphere began to be polluted with carbon monoxide, various aerosol gases containing sulfur, nitrogen, fluorine chloride, phosphorus, metal compounds such as lead, mercury, aluminum. In turn, this can lead to climate change, the gradual exhaustion of permafrost at the poles of the planet and high mountains.

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Another important pollution is agriculture. Farmers add phosphorus, nitrogen, and potassium to Mineral fertilizers in excess of the norm in order to achieve high yields. These substances, however, disrupt the cyclical cycle in nature, accumulating in the soil, fruits and their excess in water leads to human damage. As an example, the monoculture of cotton in our country has led to a violation of the soil structure and degradation of crops.

Reflecting on environmental problems, it is impossible not to mention the destruction of the ozone layer, discovered in 1974. The reason for this is the absorption of the atomic chlorine ion O₃, which leads to the decomposition of freon and freon in the atmosphere. The same situation, called the "ozone hole", was initially observed over the territories of

South America adjacent to Antarctica, and in recent years over the northern latitudes of Eurasia.

Currently, waste disposal technologies remain the only way to avoid environmental pollution. Technologies for processing residual substances and recycling waste into another industry are being created. The technology of obtaining fuel and energy in environmentally friendly ways reduces environmental pollution.

Summing up, we can say that our current dynamic century is impossible without the chemical industry. The chemical industry is used in all areas. At the same time, a lot of harmful substances and gases are released with the produced. This leads to environmental pollution, harmful gases in nature, pollution of reservoirs. Pollution of nature causes the growth of diseases. To avoid this, it is necessary to use waste-free technologies.

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